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Title: SOP for syringe & LS TOOL cleaning of GC Exploris

Date: 1.11.2024

Version: version 1

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Summary

This section describes how to clean the syringe and LS TOOL used for the TriPlus RSH autosampler. Needle clogging is the most common problem encountered when using automatic sample preparation with the TriPlus RSH autosampler. In particular, it has been observed that small parts of the LS TOOL can be released during vortexing when the magnetic end of the tool strikes the metal lid of the vial. These small particles can then clog the syringe during pipetting.

To prevent this, a different LS TOOL can be used solely for vortexing during automatic sample preparation. Alternatively, multiple syringes and LS TOOLS can be employed, which are automatically washed at regular intervals. NOTE: In the current method, 3 LS TOOLS & 3 syringes are used but 6 LS TOOLS & 6 syringes are available on TriPlusRSH autosampler, see Figure 2.

Another way is to use a wider needle diameter or the other end of the needle. Clogging of the needle may also occur when pipetting the final layer of the extract.

Always place the components on a clean, lint-free surface (aluminum foil)

How to clean the LC syringe

Cleaning the syringe is advisable before or after daily measurements and batch processing. Follow these steps to clean the syringe:

1. Remove the syringe from the LS TOOL.
2. Clean the black end of the LS TOOL using a moistened paper tissue.
3. Completely remove the syringe plunger and gently clean it with a moistened paper tissue.

4. Fill another syringe with solvent and fill the body of the syringe. Reinsert the syringe plunger and move it down. Place the end of the syringe in the ultrasonic bath and repeat this process several times.
5. Then gently move the syringe plunger along its entire length, drawing in an organic solvent, and repeat this process several times (for example, 50% isopropanol in water followed by isooctane).
6. Reinstall the syringe into the LS TOOL.

How to insert an LC Syringe into the LS TOOL

7. Remove the retaining nut from the LS TOOL, then insert the syringe, **see Figure 1**.
8. Insert the syringe body guiding the needle tip into the upper and the lower needle guide. Press the syringe firmly into the LS TOOL holder.
9. Tighten the retaining nut.

NOTE: The needle tip should not be visible outside of the lower needle guide.

NOTE: It is recommended to change the magnetic end of the LS TOOL at certain time intervals.

**Figure 1. Syringe insertion into LC TOOL; (TriPlus RSH
Hardware Manual, ThermoFisher Scientific)**

**Method for cleaning syringes at the beginning/ending of
the sequence**

NOTE: This method only contains settings for TriPlus RSH. Chromeleon 7 software does not allow skipping the GC and MS methods. The length of the GC MS method is therefore set to 0.5 min at a constant GC oven temperature of 80 C and the floated filament for the MS method (cannot be set to 0 min).

Used syringes:

100 µL FN GT SYRINGE, 57MM LGTH23S GAUGE, CONE; cat. FA22-365H2141; Thermo Scientific

10 µL FN GT SYRINGE; 57MM LGTH23S GAUGE; CONE; cat. 365D0311; Thermo Scientific

GC Inlets (TRACE1300/1310)

The settings are the same as the Instrumental method.

GC Oven Settings (Trace 1300/1310)

Prep Run Timeout	25 min	
Oven equilibration time	0.5 min	
Ready delay	0.0 min	
Mode	Constant temperature	at 80°C

GC Aux Heaters (TRACE1300/1310)

The settings are the same as the used "Instrumental method".

MSDevice (Orbitrap Exploris GC 240)

The settings are the same as the Instrumental method. The filament is off. Method Duration is 0.5 min (because of the inability to set 0 min in Chromeleon 7 software)

Autosampler settings

NOTE: At the beginning/end of the sequence, it is ideal to clean and sonicate the LS TOOL & syringe manually as described above. If this is not possible use the automatic method.

This method for cleaning the syringes is suitable at the beginning and end of the sequence. All needles are cleaned in this method.

1.	Use Tool	Tool	LS1 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)	
2.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
		Wash Index	1	
		Fill Speed	5	µL/s
		Wash Cycles	9	
		Wash Volume	70	%
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
		Dispense Speed	20	µL/s
3.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
		Wash Index	2	
		Fill Speed	5	µL/s
		Wash Cycles	9	
		Wash Volume	70	%
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
		Dispense Speed	20	µL/s
4.	Use Tool	Tool	LS2 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)	
5.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
		Wash Index	1	
		Fill Speed	5	µL/s
		Wash Cycles	9	
		Wash Volume	70	%
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
		Dispense Speed	100	µL/s
6.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
		Wash Index	2	
		Fill Speed	5	µL/s
		Wash Cycles	9	
		Wash Volume	70	%
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
		Dispense Speed	100	µL/s
7.	Use Tool	Tool	LS3 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)	
8.	Clean syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
		Wash Index	1	
		Fill Speed	5	µL/s
		Wash Cycles	9	
		Wash Volume	70	%
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm

	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s
9. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
	Wash Index	2	
	Fill Speed	5	μL/s
	Wash Cycles	9	
	Wash Volume	70	%
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s
10. Use Tool	Tool	LS5 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)	
11. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
	Wash Index	1	
	Fill Speed	5	μL/s
	Wash Cycles	9	
	Wash Volume	70	%
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s
12. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
	Wash Index	2	
	Fill Speed	5	μL/s
	Wash Cycles	9	
	Wash Volume	70	%
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s
13. Use Tool	Tool	LS6 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)	
14. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
	Wash Index	1	
	Fill Speed	5	μL/s
	Wash Cycles	9	
	Wash Volume	70	%
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s
15. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
	Wash Index	2	
	Fill Speed	5	μL/s
	Wash Cycles	9	
	Wash Volume	70	%
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s

16. Use Tool	Tool	LS7 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)	
17. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
	Wash Index	1	
	Fill Speed	5	μL/s
	Wash Cycles	9	
	Wash Volume	70	%
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s
18. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	
	Wash Index	2	
	Fill Speed	5	μL/s
	Wash Cycles	9	
	Wash Volume	70	%
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25	mm
	Dispense Speed	100	μL/s
19. Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	GC	GC1	
20. Set Output Signal (GC)	GC	GC1	

Method for cleaning syringes before every 7 samples

For every 7 samples, one Instrumental method is used, containing a set of three syringes used in this method see sequence settings. To reduce the probability of needle clogging, a different set of LS TOOLS & 100 μL syringes is used for every 14 samples, and a LS TOOL & different 10 μL syringe is used for every 21 samples. This method for cleaning syringes is performed before every 7 samples. Used syringes are not thrown away after use, but they are just cleaned and used for the next samples.

GC Inlets (TRACE1300/1310)

The settings are the same as the Instrumental method.

GC Oven Settings (Trace 1300/1310)

Prep Run Timeout	25 min	
Oven equilibration time	0.5 min	
Ready delay	0.0 min	
Mode	Constant temperature	at 80°C

GC Aux Heaters (TRACE1300/1310)

The settings are the same as the Instrumental method.

MSDevice (Orbitrap Exploris GC 240)

The settings are the same as the Instrumental method. The filament is off.

Autosampler settings

1.	Use Tool	Tool	LS2 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)
2.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1
		Wash Index	1
		Fill Speed	5 µL/s
		Wash Cycles	4
		Wash Volume	70 %
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm
		Dispense Speed	20 µL/s
3.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 2
		Wash Index	2
		Fill Speed	5 µL/s
		Wash Cycles	4
		Wash Volume	70 %
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm
		Dispense Speed	20 µL/s
4.	Use Tool	Tool	LS1 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)
5.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1
		Wash Index	1
		Fill Speed	5 µL/s
		Wash Cycles	4
		Wash Volume	70%
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm
		Dispense Speed	100 µL/s
6.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1
		Wash Index	2
		Fill Speed	5 µL/s
		Wash Cycles	4
		Wash Volume	70 %
		Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm
		Dispense Speed	100 µL/s
7.	Use Tool	Tool	LS3 (select the tool according to the Instrumental method)
8.	Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1
		Wash Index	1

	Fill Speed	5 µL/s
	Wash Cycles	4
	Wash Volume	70 %
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s
9. Clean Syringe	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1
	Wash Index	2
	Fill Speed	5 µL/s
	Wash Cycles	4
	Wash Volume	70 %
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s
10. Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	GC	GC1
11. Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	GC	GC1
	Signal	Injected

Sequence setting

Name	Instrument Method
syringe clean	method for cleaning the syringe at the beginning/end of the sequence
1_instrumental_blank	method 15m_PTV 6uL
2_instrumental_blank	method 15m_PTV 6uL
3_instrumental_blank	method 15m_PTV 6uL
4_Alkane_mix	method 15m_PTV 6uL
5_PCB_mix	method 15m_PTV 6uL
6_instrumental_blank	method 15m_PTV 6uL
7_procedural_blank	method 15m_PTV 6uL 9 temp 5C
8_external_long_term_QC	method 15m_PTV 6uL 9 temp 5C
9_NIST_1958	method 15m_PTV 6uL 9 temp 5C
10_NIST_1957	method 15m_PTV 6uL 9 temp 5C
11_NIST_1950	method 15m_PTV 6uL 9 temp 5C
12_sample_1	method 15m_PTV 6uL 9 temp 5C
13_sample_2	method 15m_PTV 6uL 9 temp 5C
syringe clean	needle clean 1
14_sample_3	method 15m_PTV 6uL 18 temp 5C
15_sample_4	method 15m_PTV 6uL 18 temp 5C
16_sample_5	method 15m_PTV 6uL 18 temp 5C
17_sample_6	method 15m_PTV 6uL 18 temp 5C
18_sample_7	method 15m_PTV 6uL 18 temp 5C
19_sample_8	method 15m_PTV 6uL 18 temp 5C
20_sample_9	method 15m_PTV 6uL 18 temp 5C
syringe clean	needle clean 2

21_sample_10	method 15m_PTV 6uL 27 temp 5C
22_sample_11	method 15m_PTV 6uL 27 temp 5C
23_sample_12	method 15m_PTV 6uL 27 temp 5C
24_sample_13	method 15m_PTV 6uL 27 temp 5C
25_sample_14	method 15m_PTV 6uL 27 temp 5C
26_sample_15	method 15m_PTV 6uL 27 temp 5C
27_sample_16	method 15m_PTV 6uL 27 temp 5C
syringe clean	needle clean 2
28_sample_17	method 15m_PTV 6uL 36 temp 5C
29_sample_18	method 15m_PTV 6uL 36 temp 5C
30_sample_19	method 15m_PTV 6uL 36 temp 5C
31_sample_20	method 15m_PTV 6uL 36 temp 5C
32_sample_21	method 15m_PTV 6uL 36 temp 5C
33_sample_22	method 15m_PTV 6uL 36 temp 5C
34_sample_23	method 15m_PTV 6uL 36 temp 5C
syringe clean	needle clean 3
35_sample_24	method 15m_PTV 6uL 45 temp 5C
36_sample_25	method 15m_PTV 6uL 45 temp 5C
37_sample_26	method 15m_PTV 6uL 45 temp 5C
38_sample_27	method 15m_PTV 6uL 45 temp 5C
39_sample_28	method 15m_PTV 6uL 45 temp 5C
40_sample_29	method 15m_PTV 6uL 45 temp 5C
41_sample_30	method 15m_PTV 6uL 45 temp 5C
syringe clean	needle clean 3
41_sample_31	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
42_sample_32	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
43_sample_33	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
44_sample_34	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
45_sample_35	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
46_sample_36	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
47_sample_37	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
syringe clean	needle clean 4
48_sample_38	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
49_external_long_term_QC	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
50_procedural_blank	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
51_NIST_1950	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
52_NIST_1957	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
53_NIST_1958	method 15m_PTV 6uL 54 temp 5C
54_PCB_mix	method 15m_PTV 6uL
55_Alkane_mix	method 15m_PTV 6uL
56_instrument_blank	method 15m_PTV 6uL

syringe clean

method for cleaning the syringe at the beginning/end of the sequence

Annex 1

TriPlusRSH Configuration

Figure 2. The modules installed on TriPlusRSH used for on-line liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) sample preparation: Temperature Controlled Drawer (1); Trayholder with adapter for 2mL vials (2); Vortexer (3); GC1 (4); Standard Wash station (5); Solvent Station (6); Centrifuge (7); Fast Wash Station (8); ATC Station (9); ATC station

Application

Version 1.4.0.4

Support Key 62KH-BREC

Robot

Robot Type Robotic Tool Change – RTC

Product Version 2.5.57.2

Edition Thermo

Tools

LS1 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365H2141

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 100 μ L

LS2 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365D0271

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 10 μ L

LS3 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365H2141

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 100 μ L

LS5 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365H2141

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 100 μ L

LS6 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365H2141

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 100 μ L

LS7 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365D0271

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 10 µL

Modules

Vortexer: vortexing with 1 positions for 2 mL (3)

Centrifuge (7)

GC1 (4)

Ready GCReady1

Injected Injected1

Prepare none

Ptv (4)

ATC Station 1 (9)

ATC Station 2 (9)

GCReady1

Source TTLIn2

Injected1

Destination SWOut2

Solvent Station: containing 2x200 mL vials (6)

Temperature Controlled Drawer: 2x 54 positions tray (1)

Drawer 1

Slot1

Rack Type VT54

Rack Item 2-CV Magnetic

Slot2

Rack Type VT54

Rack Item 2-CV Magnetic

Trayholder with adapter for 2mL vials (2)

Slot1

Rack Type VT54

Rack Item 2-CV Magnetic

Fast Wash Station (8)**Standard Wash Station: 5x 10 mL vials (5)**

Annex 2

The settings of Autosampler's modules used for this method are listed below:

Note: Other modules can be added to the ATC also other modules are installed to the autosampler

LS1

- Location: Slot 2
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365H2141

LS2

- Location: RobotArmLeft
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365D0271

LS3

- Location: Slot 3
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365H2141

Vortexer 1

- Pos2 Vial Type: None
- Actual Position 0.23 deg

DrawerTempCtrl 1

- Drawer 1
- Actual Temp: 4.9 °C
- Max Temperature: 40.0 °C
- Min Temperature: 4.0 °C
- Stdbby Temp control: on
- Stdbby Temperature: 4.0 °C
- Temp Setpoint: 5.0 °C
- Close Current: 500 mA
- Close Speed: 15 %
- Drawer Sensors: Activated
- FanSpeed: 100 %
- Open Current: 400 mA
- Open Speed: 15%
- PeltierTemperature: -1.6 °C
- Strip Distance X: 15.0 mm
- Temp Offset: 0 d °C

Thayholder 1

- Slot 1
- Cap Type: MagnetCap
- Rack Item: 2-CV Magnetic
- Tray Type: VT54

Large Solvent 1

- Pos 1 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 45.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 40.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 73.0 mm
 - > Height: 55.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 100SR
 - > Volume: 100.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 2 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 45.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 40.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 73.0 mm

- > Height: 55.0 mm
- > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
- > Vial Type: 100SR
- > Volume: 100.0 mL
- > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

Standard Wash 1

- Pos 1 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 μ L
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 2 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 μ L
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 3 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 μ L
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 4 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 μ L
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm

- > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
- > Diameter: 22.0 mm
- > Height: 49.0 mm
- > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
- > Vial Type: 10SR
- > Volume: 10.0 mL
- > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

- Waste > Max Ndl Penetr Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 20.000 mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: Waste Vial
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

Fast Solvent Wash

- MaxFlowRate: 60 μ L/s
- PostRinseLiner: 1
- PreRinseLiner: 0
- Def Ndl Penetr De: 25.000 mm
- Depenetration Sp: 100 mm/s
- Max Ndl Penetr D: 78.000 mm
- Penetration Spee: 40 mm/s
- Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

Centrifuge 1

- Board
- Drive
 - >Actual Speed: 0 rpm
 - >Actual Position: 45.09 deg
- Actual g-Force: 0
- Actual Rotor Team: 24.6°C
- Actual Speed: 0 rpm
- Auto Stop: 3.0 min

PTV

- Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 35.000 mm
- Max Ndl Penetr Depth: 100.0 mm
- Min Ndl Penetr Depth: 18.0 mm
- Position Tolerance: 4.00 mm
- Z Tolerance: 20.0 mm

RobotArmLeft

- NdlGd motor 1 > Actual Position: -3 μm
- Plunger motor 1 > Actual Position: 25 μm
> Check Plunger :
- Tool control 1 > LS5 > Location: RobotArmLeft
 - > Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
 - > Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
 - > Length: 135.0 mm
 - > Syringe Type: SYT365F2141
 - > NdlGuide Coupling: 8708
 - > Plg. Coupling Count: 8708
 - > Tool Coupling Count: 8708
- X axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 259.998 μm
> Total Axis Length: 1.208 m
- Y axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 0 μm
- Z axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 0 μm
- Acceleration Factor: 10 %
- Default strategy: parallel
- DefaultWaste: none
- Homing Strategy: Default

ATC Station 1

- Slot 1 > LS3 > Location: Slot 1
 - > Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
 - > Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
 - > Length: 135.0 mm
 - > Syringe Type: SYT365H02141
 - > ParkSlotIndex: 1
 - > ToolPresent:
 - > Fiber Protection:
- Slot 2 > LS1 > Location: Slot 2
 - > Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
 - > Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
 - > Length: 135.0 mm
 - > Syringe Type: SYT365H2141
 - > ParkSlotIndex: 2
 - > ToolPresent:
 - > Fiber Protection:
- Slot 3 > ParkSlotIndex: 3
 - > ToolPresent:
 - > Fiber Protection:
- ToolEepromAccess:

Input Output 1

- Immediate > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
- OptoIn1 > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- PWMOut: > Signal On:
 - > OutputVoltage: 0 mV
- ResetButton: > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
- Simulated: > Signal On:
 - > Trigger Event: None
 - > Waiting Time: 60.0 s
- Software In > Signal On:
- Software Out: > Signal On:
- SWOut1 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- SWOut2: > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn1 > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn2 Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn3 Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut1 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut2 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut3 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- Beep Volume: 4

GC1

- Cryo Trap: None
- Fake Inj Delay: 15000 ms
- Injected: Start
- Prepare: None
- Ready: Gready

GCRReady

- Signal On:
- BlockingTime: 0 ms
- Source: TTLIn1

Start

- Signal On:
 - Destination: SWOut1
 - DestinationAux: None
 - PulseDuration: 300 ms
-